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Building researcher
capability

**A baseline study of researcher
development in UK and Australian
universities**

September 2025

Building researcher capability

A baseline study of researcher development in UK and Australian universities

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Executive summary

Introduction

This report describes a baseline evidence-base of researcher development activity in the UK and Australia, exploring universities' strategy, policy, structures, resourcing and delivery of researcher development.

The 14 universities in this study collectively support around 40,000 research students and staff yet operate their development programmes with central teams averaging fewer than seven full-time equivalent staff. This striking finding from the survey illustrates the resource challenges facing researcher development in the UK and Australian higher education sectors.

At a time when research excellence increasingly depends on sophisticated skills in areas from AI to impact generation, the evidence illustrates the challenges of matching strategic ambition with operational reality. These challenges include:

- only a minority of institutions have dedicated researcher development strategies;
- responsibility for researcher development is widely shared across different institutional units;¹ and
- despite awareness of its importance, lack of recognition of researcher development activity in workload remains the dominant barrier to participation.

For institutional leaders and policymakers, these findings provide essential intelligence for strategic decision-making. The evidence establishes benchmarks for resourcing, identifies successful approaches through detailed case studies, and highlights areas requiring sector-wide attention.

The context of researcher development

Researcher development activity is a crucial factor in building the skills, knowledge and capability to enable and deliver excellent research. In the UK, the [Concordat to Support the Career Development of Researchers](#) drives activity to improve employment and support of research staff.

In Australia, the [Australian Code for Responsible Conduct of Research](#) drives researcher development activity to "provide ongoing training and education that promotes and supports responsible research conduct for all researchers and those in other relevant roles" and to ensure standards in supervision of graduate students.

Overview of the researcher development study

This report summarises the findings from a baseline study of researcher development strategies and activities in 14 universities in Australia (9) and in the UK (5).

The study was undertaken by [Research Consulting](#), a mission-driven business working to improve the effectiveness and impact of research and scholarly communication. Since 2013, Research Consulting has designed and managed a series of benchmarking reviews identifying common practices, resourcing levels, trends and challenges in research support functions in the UK and internationally. The study was developed and delivered

¹ The term 'institutional units' is used throughout this report to refer to structures or functions within an institution that may have responsibility for researcher development, such as central researcher development teams, doctoral colleges / academies, the library, careers service, HR or faculties / colleges.

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in partnership with **Vitae**, the global leader in supporting the professional development of researchers, experienced in working with institutions as they strive for research excellence, innovation and impact. During the course of this study, Vitae published a refreshed configuration of its sector-leading **Researcher Development Framework**. Finally, Mark Hochman, Australia expert for the project, brings over 30 years of experience as a senior manager in university research offices and through his work as director of Research Management Resources.

As this is the first time the study has been conducted, it aims to establish a baseline to describe researcher development activity across a range of institutions, and to inform discussions about broader questions, such as the appropriate level of professional development activity to be undertaken by professional and academic staff.

Areas of investigation

The survey explored key areas of researcher development strategy and activity, including internal and external motivations for researcher development, strategy and governance, structures and resourcing, operational delivery and topics covered, perceived barriers to engagement, activities to encourage engagement, and perceptions of opportunities and challenges over the next five years.

Purpose of this report

This report is the final project output and is released as a public report to support further work and development in this area. The report presents baseline data from 14 universities.

The data relating to individual universities is anonymised, but we identify key differences between UK and Australian approaches and establish ranges of current practice that may be helpful to those in strategic and operational leadership roles.

As the first iteration of the study, it provides a snapshot of current activity rather than trends over time, creating a foundation for future longitudinal analysis.

About the survey

The survey was open for responses between January and April 2025. Bespoke institutional reports and supporting analysis were delivered in May and June 2025, followed by institution-specific feedback meetings and virtual good practice workshops in July 2025.

Overall findings

Researcher development strategy and governance: shared motivations, different contexts

The survey asked about motivating factors within the institution (internal motivations) and motivating factors arising from outside the institution (external motivation) for researcher development activities, influence of third-party organisations on researcher development strategy and policy, governance structures, and coverage of researcher development strategy in relevant institutional policy documents.

Survey responses indicated that internal motivating factors are similar between Australia and the UK, particularly *alignment with institutional strategy and values*, the *intrinsic value of these activities* and *aiming to improve research culture*. However, understandably external motivations and influential third parties vary by country and include national initiatives relating to research assessment and guidance or standards for researcher development.

In both Australia and the UK, research committees are responsible for the governance of the researcher development strategy. However, only a minority of institutions have a

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formal researcher development strategy and this is often split across several different documents.

Institutions vary significantly in the number of institutional units which are described as having primary responsibility for researcher development strategy

Institutions vary significantly in the number of institutional units which are described as having primary responsibility for researcher development strategy, ranging from those which appear to favour multi-focal approaches with four to six institutional units having primary responsibility for this, to other institutions where just one central unit has primary responsibility. In other institutions, there is no institutional unit identified as having primary responsibility for researcher development strategy, but instead six or seven institutional units have shared responsibility. This sharing of responsibility appears to be based on differing areas of specialisation and relative proximity to researchers' activity, rather than implying a lack of co-ordination of researcher development strategy and delivery.

The institutional functions which most frequently have either primary or shared responsibility for researcher development strategy are *Central researcher development teams*, followed closely by *University Research Executive functions*, and *doctoral colleges or academies*. Faculties and colleges very frequently have shared responsibility for researcher development.

Central researcher development roles are characterised by widespread use of fractional FTE

Full-time equivalent staff numbers (FTE) for central researcher development roles appear to be characterised by widespread use of fractional staff time.² Headcounts of staff in central roles ranged from 2 to 69 (mean 24). However, institutions reported total FTE ranging from 0.95 FTE to 15.3 FTE (mean 6.6 FTE). Half (7) of the 14 institutions reported less than 5 FTE. It appears that many staff are doing researcher development activity as a fractional part of their broader substantive roles, although in some cases there is also use of part-time staff.

There is no obvious relationship between the size of an institution's researcher community and its level of central researcher development staff resourcing based on data from participating Australian and UK institutions.

Coverage of topics is broadest for personal effectiveness and professional skills and for research students and staff

The survey asked about which topics are covered within the researcher development offer for people in different roles and at different career stages. These topics were clustered into three thematic areas:

- management and leading;
- personal effectiveness and professional skills; and
- aspects of the research system.

Coverage appears to be broadest (larger numbers of institutions covering a larger numbers of topics) for *personal effectiveness and professional skills*, followed by *aspects of the research system*, and then *management and leading*.

² The term 'fractional staff time' is used throughout this report to indicate that many staff members engage in researcher development activities as part of broader roles, rather than being fully dedicated to these activities. This is a known feature of how researcher development activity is delivered.

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For PGRs/HDRs and academic research staff, there appears to be a slightly wider range of topics offered within Australian institutions. This may partly reflect the difference in size between the UK and Australian institutions.

Provision of researcher development opportunities on these topics for professional and technical staff is generally more limited. The broadest range of topics offered for these groups in some of the Australian institutions is in the thematic area of *management and leading*. UK respondents indicate their broadest range of provision for professional and technical staff in relation to *personal effectiveness and professional skills* and *the wider research system*.

The central researcher development team and doctoral academy lead on operational delivery and most activity is delivered through synchronous sessions

In terms of the delivery of researcher development activities, the central researcher development team & doctoral academy are most frequently involved in operational delivery.

Most activity is delivered through synchronous sessions, and approaches to delivery have been significantly influenced by the move online during the COVID pandemic. Where attempts have been made to encourage a return to in-person engagement, these appear to have had low or inconsistent uptake. Hybrid delivery (where a session offers options for participation both online and in-person) is also noted as challenging. Blended approaches – where a programme is delivered through a mixture of online and in-person sessions (and potentially mixing synchronous and asynchronous engagement) – have more potential to optimise engagement and to enable in-person interaction when facilitating networking or collaboration is a priority.

Sessions for postgraduate students more often feature asynchronous delivery and some institutions have marked differences in delivery mechanisms for research staff, compared to delivery for PGRs / HDRs.

The study illustrates the importance and challenges of effective evaluation

In the context of financial pressures and limited resources, effective evaluation is essential for focusing resources efficiently and to justify investment in researcher development. The need for evaluation is also driven by external compliance or assessment and to share good practice, assess impact, and inform programme development.

Institutions use a range of models and approaches to evaluate activity, but there are significant challenges, particularly in relation to gathering longitudinal data. This is reflected in the tension between the relative ease of collecting session feedback or embedding feedback requests in online courses and the difficulty of gathering evidence of personal growth over time or of the influence of development activities on an individual's career trajectory.

There are also related issues about the level of granularity at which researcher development activities and needs are evaluated, such as evaluation or needs analysis which focuses on the individual researcher, a session, a programme, a cohort or at a broader institutional level.

The survey explored barriers to engagement, as well as future challenges and opportunities

The survey explored methods of increasing engagement and barriers to participation. Despite clear articulation of the value of researcher development activity, perceived lack of recognition of researcher development in workload allocation remains the dominant barrier to participation.

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AI is seen as a challenge and an opportunity, with a rapidly evolving landscape of new development needs in this area, as well as opportunities to use AI in designing and delivering development activities. At a time of significant financial pressures, institutions also see opportunities for increased collaboration, including through sharing of resources and access to training.

Areas for future consideration

Based on the findings of this project, both from the survey and from extensive and sustained engagement with the participating institutions throughout the study, eight key areas have been identified for future consideration and potential sector-wide action and for review through a future researcher development survey. These areas for action include:

1. developing **robust and effective approaches to evaluation**, including longitudinal evaluation;
2. exploring change over time in the breadth of **researcher development opportunities offered to professional and technical staff**;
3. exploring options for **optimising the balance of synchronous and asynchronous delivery**, and between online and in-person delivery, and how these vary for different audiences;
4. exploring additional **opportunities for sharing good practice**. In Australia this includes interest in developing a national researcher development framework;
5. considering **how AI will influence researcher development**, both as an emerging area of development need and as a tool for delivery;
6. deepening understanding of **researcher development as a product of, and influence on, research culture** and by extension institutional culture;
7. considering the **highly fractional nature of researcher development activities** within people's roles; and
8. developing further areas for collaboration, **including access to shared training and resources**.

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1. Introduction

Overview of the researcher development survey This report summarises the findings from a survey of researcher development strategies and activities in 14 universities in Australia (9) and in the UK (5).

As this is the first time the study has been conducted, it aims to establish a baseline to describe researcher development activity across a range of institutions, creating a foundation for future longitudinal analysis.

It also aims to inform discussions about broader questions, such as the appropriate level of professional development activity to be undertaken by professional and academic staff.

Purpose of this report This report is the final project output and is released as a public report to support further work and development in this area.

The report presents baseline data from 14 universities. The data relating to individual universities is anonymised, but we identify key differences between UK and Australian approaches and establish ranges of current practice that may be helpful to those in strategic and operational leadership roles.

The context of researcher development in the UK and Australia Researcher development activity is a crucial factor in building the skills, knowledge and capability to enable and deliver excellent research. In the UK, the [Concordat to Support the Career Development of Researchers](#) drives activity to improve employment and support of research staff. It emphasises the importance of continuous professional and career development to equip and support researchers to be adaptable and flexible in an increasingly diverse global research environment and employment market, within which researchers pursue a wide range of careers. The main government funding body for research, UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), also catalyses support for researcher development through its [People and Teams Action Plan](#), and profession-specific initiatives such as the [Technician Commitment Action Plan](#). Other initiatives relating to research culture, such as the [People, Culture and Environment pilot](#) ahead of the Research Excellence Framework (REF) 2029 emphasise the importance of “embedding professional and career development at all levels and across all roles”, showing the importance of researcher development in building positive culture in research and institutions.

In Australia, the [Australian Code for Responsible Conduct of Research](#) drives researcher development activity to “provide ongoing training and education that promotes and supports responsible research conduct for all researchers and those in other relevant roles” and to ensure standards in supervision of graduate students. The [Australian Council of Graduate Research Quality](#) also advocates for high standards of research training for postgraduate students (Higher Degree by Research (HDR) programmes).

About the survey The survey explored key areas of researcher development strategy and activity, including internal and external motivations for researcher development, strategy and governance, structures and resourcing, operational delivery and topics covered, perceived barriers to engagement, activities to encourage engagement, and perceptions of opportunities and challenges over the next five years. There were two routes to complete the survey, either with a single combined response to all questions for all researcher development activity, covering both PGR (post-graduate research) and HDR (higher degree by research)

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students and research staff or with separate responses to some questions which distinguished between delivery for PGRs/HDRs and for research staff.

The survey was open for responses between January and April 2025.

Bespoke institutional reports and supporting analysis were delivered in May and June 2025, followed by institution-specific feedback meetings and virtual good practice workshops in July 2025.

Figure 1. Overview of participants by PGR/HDR and research staff (research-only and teaching & research) numbers

About the participants

The participating institutions have a range of different approaches and structures for developing researcher development strategy and undertaking researcher development delivery activity.

There are also significant differences in the size of participating institutions (Figure 1), with numbers of Postgraduate by Research (PGR – UK) or Higher Degree by Research (HDR – Australia) ranging from 85 to 4,260 in the 2023 to 2024 year³.

Acknowledgements

We would like to acknowledge and thank all those people in each participating institution who participated in this project at every stage, including early stages of co-creating survey questions, provision of data, discussions in institutional feedback meetings, and in the good practice workshops. An additional thank you is extended to those universities and individuals who have supplied and approved case studies for this report.

Although we have anonymised the data relating to *individual* universities, we are able to confirm the names of the 14 participating universities.

Australia

Curtin University
Edith Cowan University
Flinders University
Macquarie University
RMIT University
University of Newcastle

UK

Bath Spa
Loughborough University
University of Greenwich
University of the West of England
University of Westminster

³ PGR/HDR data for the calendar year 2024 in Australia and for the academic year 2023-24 in the UK.

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University of New South Wales
University of Technology Sydney
Western Sydney University

2. Strategy and drivers for researcher development

Introduction

The survey asked about internal and external motivations for researcher development activities, the influence of third-party organisations on researcher development strategy and policy, governance structures, and coverage of researcher development strategy in relevant institutional policy documents.

This section also includes two case studies: one including a) examining supporting institutional objectives relating to external initiatives and b) accreditation through internal collaboration between teams, and the second exploring the effect of expressed researcher demand on shaping researcher development strategy.

Internal motivating factors are similar between Australia and the UK...

Respondents were asked to make up to three selections from a multiple-choice list of significant internal factors motivating their institution to offer researcher development activity.

Across all participating institutions, *alignment with institutional strategy and values* was the strongest internal motivating factor for offering researcher development activities, followed closely by the *intrinsic value of these activities*. A majority of the participating institutions also indicated that *aiming to improve research culture* was one of the top three internal motivations. Only one institution indicated that *expressed demand from researchers* was amongst the top three most significant internal motivating factors.

Figure 2. Top three internal motivating factors for researcher development activity

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...whilst external motivations and influential third parties vary by country

There are some similarities in the external motivating factors for offering researcher development between Australian and UK institutions. For example, *research excellence assessments* (REF in the UK and the paused ERA (Excellence in Research for Australia) process in Australia), the *European HR Excellence in Research Award* and the *Vitae Researcher Development Framework* have a strong motivating role in both the UK and Australia. As one might predict, country-specific initiatives such as the *Concordat to Support the Career Development of Researchers* (UK) and the *Australian Code for Responsible Conduct of Research* (Australia) are the most significant external factors overall.

A key difference between countries is evident in how institutions source expertise: Australian participants draw on a significantly wider range of third-party organisations to inform their researcher development strategy compared to their UK counterparts. The *Australian Council of Graduate Research* is particularly influential in shaping Australian approaches, as is the *Australasian Research Management Society*, particularly through the professional development opportunities it provides. Within the UK, *Vitae* and the *UK Council of Graduate Education* emerge as the predominant external influencers. Some overlap exists across both countries, with *university networks* and *Vitae* having cross-national influence.

Case study: University of Westminster: external accreditation and internal collaboration

Researcher development strategy at the University is influenced by external initiatives and accreditation, including the principles of the *Researcher Development Concordat*, which the University has been a signatory of since 2020, the *Athena Swan Charter* to support and transform gender equality within higher education, and the *HR Excellence in Research Award* (HREiRA), which the University has held since 2016.

Informed by these external initiatives and to support the University's ongoing external accreditation activities, the University is currently reviewing researcher development support in collaboration with the University's People, Culture and Wellbeing team. This work has led to a shared understanding of the specialist nature of researcher development activities and collaborative strategic and operational engagement in developing a new platform for training. The new platform aims to integrate researcher development training conversations within professional development review cycles.

Australian participants have a broader approach to targeting career stages and roles for researcher development activity.

The survey asked about the extent to which different career stages and roles are targeted for researcher development.

There were differences between Australian and UK institutions in terms of their targeting of career stages and roles in their researcher development provision, with a wider spread of "very highly" targeted roles in Australia – including mid- and senior- level researchers as well as professional staff supporting or enabling research (Figure 3).

The targeting of researcher development provision among the UK participants is narrower, with less focus on professional research-enabling staff and external supervisors, in particular.

This may reflect the generally larger size of the Australian participating institutions, with larger institutions and larger researcher development teams having more scope to target activities at a more granular level for different career stages.

Figure 3. Targeted career stages and roles

There are similarities between governance and strategy documents in the two countries

The survey asked about governance structures and strategy documents covering researcher development. In Australian and UK institutions, research committees provide the primary governance of researcher development strategy.

Researcher development strategy is typically embedded within institutional research strategies and wider strategic plans. Only a minority of participants reported having a dedicated researcher development strategy.

Case study: Flinders University: Responding to expressed demand in researcher development strategy and programme planning

Flinders have two researcher development teams that respond to the expressed needs of their cohorts (HDR students and supervisors, research staff, and technical and professional staff). Each team has developed training based on those needs and their researcher development provision has evolved differently. These differences are exemplified by the different prioritisation of asynchronous training for HDR students and supervisors who need to complete mandatory training at set times, compared to a range of synchronous training for research staff and professional staff who support researchers, where the workshops and information sessions are delivered in real time in in-person, online or hybrid sessions. There are considerable opportunities for the teams to work together, making sure they retain their distinctiveness, and leverage it.

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For example, Flinders has created a bespoke and comprehensive online training programme Higher Degree by Research (HDR) for students. As part of this, all HDR students are required to complete an online induction within the first two months of commencing their studies. This includes undertaking a Skills Needs Analysis through an online Candidature Management tool. This generates a tailored development plan that serves as a guide for the student's training and professional development. This plan is reviewed and discussed with each student's supervisor at their next scheduled annual milestone. At each milestone review, candidates evaluate their progress toward the goals outlined in their development plan and establish new goals for the upcoming year. They can then pick from a range of online training options and workshops on those topics, and complete training relevant to them at a time that suits them. This iterative process ensures continuous development and alignment with research and career objectives. The program has been created internally, based on student need and feedback, with particular recognition of the cohort of students who are part time (37%) or external (13%) who do not attend campus. The program is evaluated and updated annually based on results from an annual student satisfaction survey, which shows that 65% of students prefer online learning that is responsive to their needs.

3. Structures and resourcing

Introduction

The survey asked about structures and resourcing for researcher development. This included questions about institutional units with responsibility for researcher development strategy, and about recent and planned changes in these structures. Data were gathered about resourcing in terms of the size and roles of central researcher development teams, as well as about the staff involved in researcher development beyond the central team, and externally-provided support for researcher development.

This section also includes a case study of doctoral student peer support roles in an Australian institution.

Institutions vary significantly in the number of institutional units which are described as having primary responsibility for researcher development strategy

The survey explored which institutional units have responsibility for researcher development strategy. All participating institutions identified more than one institutional unit as having either primary, shared or ad hoc responsibility for this.

Overall, the institutional functions which most frequently have either primary or shared responsibility for researcher development strategy are *Central researcher development teams*, followed closely by *University Research Executive functions*, and *doctoral colleges or academies*. Faculties and colleges very frequently have shared responsibility for researcher development. This sharing of responsibility appears to be based on differing areas of specialisation and relative proximity to researchers' activity, rather than implying a lack of co-ordination of researcher development strategy and delivery.

Institutions vary significantly in the number of institutional units which are described as having primary responsibility for researcher development strategy, ranging from those which appear to favour multi-focal approaches with four to six institutional units having primary responsibility for this, to other institutions where just one central unit has primary responsibility. In other institutions, there is no institutional unit identified as having primary responsibility for researcher development strategy, but instead six or seven institutional units have shared responsibility.

Recent and planned changes to structures include strategy reviews, integration or consolidation of activity between teams and programme reviews

The survey asked about changes made over the last three years or planned for the coming year.

Prominent changes made within participating institutions included: *greater integration or co-ordination of activity*, *reviewing or refreshing programmes*, or *increasing activity around specific career stages*, (such as for early- or mid-career researchers).

Changes planned for the coming year include: *strategy reviews*, *restructuring* (e.g., consolidating doctoral development within a new doctoral academy), *recruitment to new roles*, the *introduction of new programmes*, *work on new topics* or *new methods of delivery*, and the development of *internal engagement/relationships* with other research support teams.

Overall, central researcher development roles are characterised by widespread use of fractional contracts

The survey explored the size and composition of central researcher development teams. The survey used "researcher development professional" or "staff" to mean: "someone with a substantial responsibility (and at least some dedicated contracted time) for researcher development (for any career stage) in their job description".

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Overall, full-time equivalent staff numbers (FTE) for central researcher development roles appear to be characterised by widespread use of fractional contracts. Headcounts of staff in central roles ranged from 2 to 69 (mean 24). However, institutions reported total FTE (including those supporting PGRs/HDRs and research staff) ranging from 0.95 FTE to 15.3 FTE (mean 6.6 FTE). Half (7) of the 14 institutions reported less than 5 FTE. It appears that many staff are doing researcher development activity as a fractional part of their broader substantive roles, although in some cases there is also use of part-time staff.

Professional staff make up the majority of total FTE in both the Australian and UK institutions, although there is use of academic (or mixed academic and professional) roles within the central researcher development team in all but three of the institutions.

The largest share of FTE in the central researcher development team tends to be associated with either researcher developer roles (i.e., those who deliver training) or researcher development co-ordinators (i.e., those who co-ordinate activity, but do not deliver training) (Figure 4).

In the Australian institutions, it appears that the largest teams – both by headcount and FTE – are found in institutions with a medium-sized population of HDRs and research staff.

In line with similar findings from earlier studies of research contracts teams in the UK and Australia ([Managing Research Contracts 2018](#) and [Research Contracts Benchmarking 2023](#)), Australian salaries are generally slightly higher than their UK equivalents.

Figure 4. Share of central researcher development team FTE by role type (less than 5FTE shown with *)

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Among participating institutions there is no obvious relationship between researcher community size and the level of central staff resource

There is no obvious relationship between the size of an institution's researcher community and its level of central researcher development staff resourcing based on data from participating Australian and UK institutions.

Indeed, among Australian participants the largest central teams appear to be clustered among mid-sized institutions serving communities of between one to two thousand in each of the two groups (research students and staff). Anecdotal discussions with mid-sized Australian universities suggested this may reflect a recognition of the need to develop larger cohorts and percentages of research active staff.

Roles outside of central team – other institutional roles and external support

Ten institutions reported headcount data for roles outside the central researcher development function and eight reported FTE data. In contrast to the central researcher development team, the majority of these roles are academic in nature, both by headcount and FTE. Roles beyond the central function include staff in the library, as well as faculty or school-based roles, and those within research centres and institutes.

There is significant variation in the number of hours of activity delivered by external trainers or consultants and these activities included training delivery for groups and one-to-one coaching support.

Case study: Edith Cowan University: peer support for research students

The SOAR Centre (Support, Opportunities, Advice, Resources) is a free, peer-to-peer support service open to all ECU higher degree by research (HDR) and honours students, as well as ECU staff undertaking research. The SOAR Centres are staffed by SOAR Peer Advisers: Higher Degree by Research students who provide research skills support based on their own experiences as research student peers. They are available for one-to-one appointments in-person or via teleconference and they also conduct small group workshops on a variety of topics. SOAR Peer Advisers can also direct HDR students to relevant ECU support staff, such as HDR communication advisers, research methodology advisers and research support coordinators, and to training, resources and other ECU services.

Located on ECU's two Perth campuses, and open during semester and between semesters for the bulk of the year, the Centre for Learning and Teaching's SOAR Centres provide a welcoming environment for HDR students to connect with their peers. More information about the skills of the SOAR peer advisers is available at <https://intranet.ecu.edu.au/research/for-research-students/soar-centre> and more information about SOAR Sessions is available at: <https://intranet.ecu.edu.au/research/for-research-students/soar-centre/soar-sessions>

Key funding sources include guaranteed institutional funds, discretionary central budget and ringfenced research block grant funding

The survey asked about sources of funding for researcher development activities. Both Australian and UK institutions rank *guaranteed institutional funding*, *discretionary central budget*, and *ringfenced research block grant funding* as highly important funding sources.

UK institutions rank *ringfenced research block grant* as a significant source of funding. However, despite the common association of this with *support for research culture*, Australian institutions more frequently report that researcher development and research culture overlap highly or very highly, than UK institutions.

Training for researcher development professionals most frequently comes from professional bodies

The survey also explored provision of training for researcher development professionals. This is most frequently sourced from professional accreditation societies (such as ARMA or ARMS), other external providers, or provided internally (led by the institutional professional development team).

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and external or internal providers

Five responses mention Vitae (four as a selected option, one in a comment), other external providers mentioned include Epigeum, AdvanceHE fellowship, UKCGE, Intersect, Building Connections Across Europe, a statewide Community of Practice for Researcher Development, Training professionals, and the Australasian Ethics Network.

4. Delivery of programmes and activities

Introduction

The survey explored which teams are involved in the operational delivery of researcher development and asked about which topics are covered within the researcher development offer for people in different roles and at different career stages. It also explored approaches to delivery, including formats and synchronous vs asynchronous training, as well as considering the extent to which different groups of people within the institution deliver researcher development activities. This section also includes a case study of a researcher development programme to support casual academic staff transitioning to permanent research and teaching contracts.

The central researcher development team, doctoral academy, and in some cases the library, are most frequently involved in operational delivery

The survey asked about the parts of the institution which are involved in operational delivery. Responses focused mainly on the central researcher development team, the doctoral academy or similar, and in some cases, the library.

Regular structured training needs analyses are more frequently conducted for PGR/HDRs, than for research staff.

4.1 Range of topics covered by researcher development

The range of topics covered by researcher development activities varies between Australia and the UK and for different roles

The survey explored the range of topics covered by researcher development activities, and to which roles activities on these topics were offered.

For PGRs/HDRs and academic research staff, there appears to be a slightly wider range of topics covered by researcher development activities within Australian institutions. This may partly reflect the difference in size between the UK and Australian institutions.

Provision of researcher development opportunities on these topics for professional and technical staff is generally more limited. The broadest range of topics offered for these groups in some of the Australian institutions is in the thematic area of *management and leading*. UK respondents indicate their broadest range of provision for professional and technical staff in relation to *personal effectiveness and professional skills* and *the wider research system*.

Australian institutions provide a slightly wider range of opportunities for researcher development relating to **management and leading**

Participating institutions were asked what topics within the thematic area of **management and leading** were covered by the programmes delivered by researcher development professionals in the current academic year and to whom these were offered (Figure 5).

For PGRs/HDRs, the range of topics covered in both Australian and UK institutions usually includes: *research integrity and ethics* and *mental health and wellbeing*. However, Australian institutions also include: *research project management*, and *mentoring*.

For **academic research staff**, the remit of both Australian and UK institutions usually includes: *research integrity and ethics*, *research project management*, *leadership and supervising doctoral students*. The Australian institutions more frequently include *mental health and wellbeing*, *mentoring*, and *leading a research group*.

Figure 5. Management and leading: numbers of institutions covering each topic

		PGRs / HDRs	Academic staff	Professional staff	Technical staff
Australia	Research integrity and ethics	9	9	6	3
	Research project management	9	8	3	1
	Mentoring	7	7	4	1
	Mental health and wellbeing	8	6	2	2
	Equality, diversity and inclusion	3	5	4	2
	Managing budgets, finance and resources	3	6	3	2
	Leadership	4	7	3	0
	Recruitment and selection	2	4	3	2
	Supervising doctoral researchers	2	9	0	0
	Managing staff performance	0	5	3	2
	Conducting appraisals / performance reviews	1	4	2	2
	Leading a research group	1	7	0	0
UK	Research integrity and ethics	5	5	2	1
	Mental health and wellbeing	4	2	1	1
	Research project management	2	4	1	1
	Supervising doctoral researchers	0	5	1	1
	Managing budgets, finance and resources	2	2	1	1
	Equality, diversity and inclusion	2	1	1	1
	Leadership	1	4	0	0
	Mentoring	1	3	1	0
	Leading a research group	1	3	0	0
	Recruitment and selection	0	3	0	0
	Conducting appraisals / performance reviews	1	0	0	0
	Managing staff performance	0	0	0	0

There are some differences in topics offered in UK and Australian institutions within the thematic area of **personal effectiveness and professional skills**

Within the thematic area of **personal effectiveness and professional skills** there were similarities and differences between the topics offered by UK and Australian institutions (Figure 6).

For PGRs/HDRs, the remit of both Australian and UK institutions usually includes: *communication and dissemination, open research, institutional induction, career management and progression, and research methods*. However, more Australian institutions also include: *awareness of AI tools, engaging with industry and external partners, collaboration and teamworking, and personal motivation and effectiveness*. UK institutions more frequently include *teaching or lecturing*.

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For **academic research staff**, the remit of both Australian and UK institutions usually includes similar topics to those offered to PGRs/HDRs, as well as *collaboration and teamworking, engaging with industry and external partners, and applying for external grant funding*. The Australian institutions more frequently include *awareness of AI tools*. UK institutions more frequently include *teaching or lecturing and the teaching-research interface*.

Figure 6. Personal effectiveness and professional skills: numbers of institutions covering each topic

		PGRs / HDRs	Academic staff	Professional staff	Technical staff
Australia	Collaboration and teamworking	9	9	3	1
	Communication and dissemination	9	9	3	1
	Engaging with industry and external partners	9	9	4	0
	Institutional induction	8	8	3	3
	Awareness and use of AI tools at different stages of the research lifecycle	7	7	5	2
	Open research (open publication and open data)	8	8	4	1
	Project management	8	8	3	2
	Applying for external grant funding	5	9	5	0
	Career management and progression	9	7	2	1
	Personal motivation and effectiveness	7	6	2	1
	Research methods	8	6	0	0
	Interdisciplinary research	5	4	1	0
	Teaching or lecturing	3	3	1	0
	Teaching-research interface	2	2	0	0
UK	Applying for external grant funding	4	5	3	1
	Communication and dissemination	4	5	2	1
	Open research (open publication and open data)	5	5	1	1
	Engaging with industry and external partners	2	4	3	2
	Institutional induction	5	4	1	1
	Teaching or lecturing	4	3	2	2
	Collaboration and teamworking	3	5	1	1
	Project management	4	3	2	1
	Research methods	5	3	1	1
	Career management and progression	4	5	0	0
	Interdisciplinary research	2	4	1	1

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Awareness and use of AI tools at different stages of the research lifecycle	3	2	1	1
Personal motivation and effectiveness	4	1	1	1
Teaching-research interface	1	3	0	0

There are some differences in topics offered in UK and Australian institutions within the thematic area of **aspects of the research system**

In the thematic area of **aspects of the research system** there were similarities and differences between the topics offered by UK and Australian institutions (Figure 7).

For **PGRs/HDRs**, the remit of both Australian and UK institutions usually includes *research impact, commercialisation, and public engagement*. Australian institutions also include *Indigenous ways of knowing*. UK institutions more frequently include experience of *other employment sectors, and knowledge exchange*.

For **academic research staff**, the remit of both Australian and UK institutions usually includes similar topics to those offered for PGRs/HDRs, as well as *knowledge exchange*. The UK institutions more frequently include *public policy development and participation in funder, sector and institutional policy, and decision-making*.

Figure 7. Aspects of the research system: numbers of institutions covering each topic

		PGRs / HDRs	Academic staff	Professional staff	Technical staff
Australia	Research impact	9	9	4	0
	Commercialisation	8	9	4	0
	Public engagement	8	8	3	0
	Indigenous knowledges and ways of knowing	7	6	3	2
	Knowledge exchange	6	8	4	0
	Translational science	5	5	1	0
	Experience of other employment sectors	6	1	1	1
	Secondment / placement in another employment sector	6	3	0	0
	Citizen science or co creation of research with society	2	5	1	0
	Participation in institutional policy and decision-making	4	2	0	0
	Public policy development	2	4	0	0
	Participation in funder and sector policy and decision making	1	2	1	0
UK	Knowledge exchange	3	5	3	2
	Commercialisation	4	4	3	1
	Research impact	4	5	2	1
	Public engagement	4	5	1	1
	Public policy development	2	4	2	1

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Citizen science or co creation of research with society	2	2	1	1
Participation in institutional policy and decision-making	1	3	1	1
Participation in funder and sector policy and decision making	1	3	1	1
Experience of other employment sectors	3	1	0	0
Indigenous knowledges and ways of knowing	1	0	0	0
Secondment / placement in another employment sector	1	0	0	0
Translational science	1	0	0	0

Case study: Western Sydney University: Researcher development programme to support staff employed in permanent T&R contracts

In 2023 Western Sydney University committed to transitioning academic work from casual employment to ongoing positions. The target was 150 new FTE positions created and filled across 3 years.

The Researcher Future Accelerator Program (RFAP) was developed to support these staff to develop their research capacities, as the majority were previously in teaching-only roles.

The eight-module program was delivered on three occasions. It was delivered face-to-face, online and in hybrid mode. Interest from other Early Career Researchers prompted the RFAP to be made available to all research staff.

The modules were co-created with research support staff and featured experienced Western researchers across all disciplines sharing their experience and advice.

Figure 8. Modules in Western Sydney University's Researcher Futures Accelerator Program (used with permission from Western Sydney University)

4.2 Approaches to programme delivery

There are both similarities and differences between the methods of delivery used in the UK and Australia.

The survey explored how researcher development activities are delivered.

Australian and UK respondents indicate similar patterns of responses about the methods which are most frequently used to deliver researcher development. Survey responses which did not distinguish between delivery for PGRs/HDRs and for research staff indicated that *training for supervisors and managers, professional and career development training/workshops, and subject-specific activities* are used in both Australia and the UK. UK institutions refer to more use of *cross-institutional provision*, such as doctoral training partnerships (DTPs), likely reflecting greater geographical proximity.

In survey responses which gave separate responses for PGRs/HDRs and research staff, **PGR/HDR** responses indicate that *induction programmes, e-learning or self-directed resources, and competitions* are frequently used for delivery in both the UK and Australian institutions. For **research staff**, in Australia, *subject-specific delivery, professional and career development training/workshops, and mentoring and coaching* are more frequently very highly used to deliver development activities. Between the two UK institutions which gave separate responses for PGRs and research staff, *e-learning and one-to-one strategic researcher advice* are very highly used to deliver development activities.

Most activity is delivered through synchronous sessions, and approaches to delivery have been significantly influenced by the move online during the COVID-19 pandemic

The survey asked about the format of delivery of researcher development activity. Generally, in both Australian and UK participants, synchronous programme delivery makes up the majority of both sessions offered and individual participants engaged. Where responses distinguished between delivery to PGRs/HDRs and research staff, synchronous delivery dominates for **research staff**, whereas there is a more even split between synchronous and asynchronous delivery for **PGRs/HDRs**.

The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic is clearly apparent in institutional responses about the balance between online, in-person, and hybrid delivery over the last 5 years with a definite shift towards online delivery. Where attempts have been made to encourage a return to in-person engagement, these appear to have had low or inconsistent uptake. Hybrid delivery (where a session offers options for participation both online and in-person) is also noted as challenging. Blended approaches – where a programme is delivered through a mixture of online and in-person sessions (and potentially mixing synchronous and asynchronous engagement) – has more potential to optimise engagement and to enable in-person interaction, when facilitating networking or collaboration is a priority.

The teams which are ranked highest for primarily delivering researcher development activity for PGRs/HDRs are *professional staff supporting / enabling research* followed by *senior researchers* and *mid-career academics* (Australia) and *internal researcher development professionals*, followed by *senior researchers* and then *professional staff supporting / enabling research* (UK). For research staff, the groups ranked highest for delivery of activities among both the Australian and UK institutions are *researcher development professionals* and *professional staff supporting / enabling research*.

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Figure 9. Groups delivering researcher development activity for PGRs / HDRs

Figure 10. Groups delivering researcher development activity for research staff

5. Evaluation and reporting

Introduction

The survey asked about evaluation, the availability of data, and frequency of reporting of metrics about researcher development activity. Half of participants were able to include actual data for at least one metric. This section also includes a case study of evaluation of a researcher development programme in an Australian institution.

Reasons for evaluating provision include external compliance and intrinsic value of sharing good practice and informing programme development

The most frequent reasons for evaluation in UK institutions are related to external compliance or assessment, such as the *REF* process or the *Concordat to Support the Career Development of Researchers*. In Australia, the reasons for evaluation focus on *identifying and sharing good practice, internal assessment of impact, and informing programme development* (Figure 11).

In the context of financial pressures and limited resources, effective evaluation can help to focus resources efficiently and to justify investment in researcher development. It also helps to identify areas for improvement and to provide a benchmark for the comprehensiveness and quality of the researcher development offering.

Figure 11. Reasons to evaluate provision

Institutions use a range of models to evaluate researcher development, but there are significant challenges, particularly around demonstrating longitudinal change

Approaches to evaluation of researcher development programmes include the **Kirkpatrick model** which features four levels for assessing the impact of a programme, including:

- Level 1: Reaction
- Level 2: Learning
- Level 3: Behaviour
- Level 4: Results

Kellogg's logic model also offers a useful way to frame evaluation of researcher development activity, focusing on five components of resources/inputs; activities; outputs; outcomes and impact. However, effective evaluation of researcher development activity

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presents significant challenges, particularly at Kirkpatrick level 3 and 4 and in terms of impact in Kellogg's model, because these require evidencing of deeper change over time.

This is reflected in the tension between the relative ease of gathering session feedback or embedding feedback requests in online courses and the difficulty of gathering longitudinal evidence of personal growth or of the influence of development activities on an individual's career trajectory.

There are also related issues about the level of granularity at which researcher development activities are evaluated, such as evaluation which focuses on the individual researcher, a session, a programme, a cohort or at a broader institutional level.

Seven out of 14 participants were able to include actual data for at least one metric

The survey asked about which metrics or measures their institution uses for researcher development activity and how frequently these are reported.

The metrics which are most frequently available and regularly reported are total attendance at live events, live sessions / events offered (both total and unique counts) and online learning completions.

Seven out of 14 participants were able to include actual data for at least one metric (three from the UK, four from Australia). All seven provided data for live sessions/events offered (total count) and six provided data for total attendance at live events. Two institutions (one UK and one Australian) provided actual data for five or more metrics.

Australian institutions place greater emphasis on evaluating provision

The most frequently used evaluation mechanisms are feedback forms, whilst research student surveys are also frequently used and appear to provide slightly higher levels of insight. Other methods of evaluation include comprehensive internal reviews and exploration of information about external sector trends.

Australian institutions appear to place greater emphasis on evaluating their provision, as well as having greater ability for staff to record, track and monitor their own training and slightly more use of theories of change in researcher development.

Case study: RMIT University: evaluation of aligning seed funding and researcher development

RMIT provides development support in conjunction with its internal seed funding programs to support engagement and translation. An example of development support in conjunction with internal funding programs is the Strategic Impact Fund Development Program or SIF. SIF supports the development of interdisciplinary and inter-sectoral opportunities that explore diverse pathways to research impact and are aligned to RMIT's six desired Futures. Grants awarded from this fund vary in value from AU\$3,000 to AU\$50,000 (approx. £1.4k-£24k), the median award value being around \$25,000 (approx. £12k).

The accompanying development program was piloted in 2024-25 with the aims of:

- Supporting RMIT's objective of deepening impact culture and capability
- Improving the quality of the applications to the SIF
- Improving the outcomes from funded projects.
- Enabling evaluation of impact-related training along the lines of the Kirkpatrick model of training evaluation – particularly Levels 3-4 of the model, which relate to behavioural and organisational change.

Historically, while training offered through the Research & Innovation Researcher Capability Development Program regularly seeks feedback from participants about the relevance and quality of the training provided

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(Kirkpatrick levels 1 (reaction) and 2 (learning)) evaluation of researcher development provision at RMIT has rarely extended to evaluation of behavioural and organisational change (levels 3 and 4). These latter evaluation factors are crucial to determining the fitness for purpose of the fund's criteria and the institutional return on investment.

The pilot development program launched in 2024 and included:

- Application clinics – sessions for prospective applicants to discuss and test their ideas with representatives of the assessment panel;
- Impact narrative masterclass – particularly including guidance on how to identify inputs, activities, different kinds of stakeholders, outputs, outcomes and impact;
- Impact pathway planning – to enable tracking of and adjustment to the impact pathway while not losing sight of the original goal;
- Storytelling – to support non-academic stakeholder and media engagement;
- Forming, working and navigating challenges in working in interdisciplinary teams.

While alignment of development opportunities to the funding round presents a more solid basis for evaluation, the teams involved need to consider whether the size of the fund and its typical award value are sufficient incentives to undertake development when time and resources are at such a premium; and whether the content is sufficiently appropriate to the outcomes of the fund.

Early evaluation of the development program shows:

- Increased engagement with research impact-related training and development: a total of 44 attendees who may otherwise not have attended impact-related training and development, 30% of whom went on to be associated with a successful SIF application in 2025
- Improved quality of application to the funding program: approximately 50% success rate for project teams where at least one member attended at least one development program component
- While many attendees to the program did not apply for funding in 2025, this is in fact a success measure. It shows that attendees have developed a better understanding about the purpose of the fund and how it supports impact, as well as improvements in pitching and interdisciplinary skills.
- Engagement with the program was greater for the components offered prior to award announcement, than those offered once the funding had been awarded.

6. Barriers and approaches to encouraging participation

Introduction

The survey asked about barriers which affect participation in researcher development activities and approaches to encouraging participation and communicating about researcher development opportunities. This section also includes a case study about the use of theories of change and researcher development champions.

UK institutions tend to have time for development activity for researchers built into workload allocation

The participating UK institutions all report that time for researcher development activity is, to some extent, built into workload plans, either in a broadly consistent way across the institution or sometimes with significant variation across the institution. The majority of Australian institutions report that time for researcher development is not built into workload plans. Where time is built in, around 10 days a year is recommended for **research staff**. For **PGRs/HDRs**, recommended time for development activities tends to be based on degree qualification requirements or time for mandatory training. It was also noted that academics have study leave built into many contracts as well as up to 20% of workload for administrative duties - some felt these were available for professional development opportunities.

Barriers to engagement, and methods of communication and motivation

The survey asked about the extent to which a range of factors were perceived to be barriers to engagement in researcher development activities.

In Australia, the most frequently perceived barriers to participation are *lack of recognition in workload allocation* and *awareness of available opportunities*. *Recognition in workload allocation* is also perceived as very highly significant barrier in the UK responses.

Respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which they used certain methods to provide information about researcher development activities and how effective they perceived these to be. The methods which appear to be most frequently used are *email newsletters*, and *email invitations* are perceived to be highly effective.

Methods used to motivate engagement include *identifying champions at senior level* (particularly in the Australian institutions), as well as *a positive culture of development*, *line manager / supervisor support*, and *engaging researchers in the design of content* (Figure 12).

Where incentives are offered, these most frequently include *catering* (although in one case this is no longer offered due to financial pressures). *Workload allocation*, *certificates*, *competitions*, and *alignment of offerings to seed funding* are also mentioned.

Institutions were invited to share examples of effective approaches to encouraging engagement. Examples include embedding development reflections within the formal performance review process, more targeted communications about activities, and senior leadership encouragement of development activities.

Figure 12. Methods of motivating engagement

Case study: University of Newcastle: theories of change and researcher development champions

Over the last four years, the University of Newcastle has adopted and implemented Prosci’s methodology and the ADKAR model across the University. This includes using it to design researcher development programmes. This has established a common language for use across the organisation, meaning that researcher development activities are being promoted to academics in a language which is now familiar to them. It has also been used to assist the creation of action plans for personal and professional growth, with an increased appetite for these. The ADKAR methodology involves the following stages:

- A – Awareness – pre-contemplation;
- D – Desire – contemplation;
- K – Knowledge – preparation;
- A – Ability – action; and
- R – Reinforcement – maintenance.

As the organisation's change maturity evolved over time, a notable shift in mindset and behaviour emerged - from perceiving change as a singular event to embracing it as a continuous, cyclical process. This cultural transformation fostered an environment of ongoing improvement, enhancing the organisation’s capacity for agility, adaptability, and responsiveness.

Newcastle is also using the ADDIE model of instructional design, which helps them to articulate the aims of researcher development more clearly, aligned with a University vision of what success looks like for researchers who actively engage and participate in researcher development programmes, including measurable KPIs, and longitudinal evaluation of activities, outcomes, and changes in behaviour over time.

The ADDIE model features five stages of instructional design:

- Analysis – understanding the situation and the gaps to be filled;

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- Design – designing an optimum learning experience to address the gaps identified in the analysis;
- Development – building the learning end product;
- Implementation – delivering the learning end product to the audience; and
- Evaluation – reviewing the effectiveness of the learning end product and updating it as appropriate, moving back to the Analysis stage to repeat the cycle.

One specific programme which has been running for the last six years is Women in Research Fellowship (rescoped in 2024 and now known as the ADVANCE Equity in Research Fellowship). Evaluation includes establishing baseline measurements of participants, using a template to capture information needed and to learn about participants intended outcomes, actual outcomes and what has changed. The behavioural changes each participant highlights help to support the next cohort of researchers undertaking this programme.

Everyone who completes the Fellowship is known as a *Forever Fellow*, and they become ongoing champions in their colleges and schools. They also engage as mentors and each *Forever Fellow* further identifies and undertakes a legacy action item that reinforce behavioural changes and program sponsorship. In addition there is a programme evaluation workshop and debrief, with multimedia case studies produced, which are used to celebrate and promote the programme to future cohorts, and as a library of positive outcomes which individual researchers have experienced after undertaking the programme. There are follow-up touch-point surveys at one, three and five years post-completion of the programme. This Fellowship programme was used as part of Newcastle's Athena SWAN submissions, initially for bronze award with the expanded Fellowship program and outcomes to date making a significant contribution to silver award.

7. Challenges and opportunities

Introduction

The survey concluded with questions about challenges and opportunities over the next five years, as well as potential for future collaboration between institutions. This section also includes a case study of examples of successful collaboration on researcher development activities between institutions.

Challenges over the next five years include financial pressures and AI

Participants were asked to identify up to five challenges for researcher development over the next five years.

Responses reflected uncertainty, change and disruption in the wider political, economic and social landscape, and specifically the financial pressures in the sector and corresponding competition for resources. Technological changes such as the growing use of AI were also discussed.

Other responses related to challenges in providing activities on topics which meet the needs of the audience, and how to accommodate or prioritise a wide range of needs, as well as how to improve content and delivery, and communication about development activity.

In an institutional context, some responses noted the challenge of positioning researcher development activity internally in terms of perceived value of development activity and time pressures experienced by researchers in relation to undertaking development activities.

Opportunities over the next five years also include AI, together with opportunities for greater collaboration between institutions

Participants were also asked to identify up to five opportunities for researcher development over the next five years. AI appeared as an opportunity, particularly for use in developing or delivering development activities. System developments were seen as providing opportunities to consolidate development activities in a single place. Within the institutional context, there were perceived to be opportunities for researcher development to make positive contributions to research culture as well as institution-specific opportunities, such as institutional strategy development or the opening of a new campus.

Opportunities for collaboration including interdisciplinarity and working with external partners were also described, and most respondents thought there would be slightly more or a lot more opportunities for collaboration in the next five years; no institution thought it would decrease.

Opportunities for collaboration included:

- sharing resources, including training and development activities and supervision; and
- sharing good practice and providing opportunities for community-building and networking.

Case study: Bath Spa and UWE: examples of external collaboration and researcher development

For a small and specialist institution like Bath Spa University, external collaboration offers a way to work with partners to offer shared training and events. [Guild HE](#) is a sector mission group with members committed to "providing vocationally-focused higher education... in a range of specialised fields". The group is currently

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developing Equality, Diversity and Inclusion training for REF, and they have also arranged shared doctoral events and shared training and provide access to shared services and systems. The University is also a co-lead (with the University of Exeter) of the [British Academy Early Career Research Network Regional Cluster](#) for the Southwest and South Wales, which includes nine universities over a large geographical area. The Cluster aims to support the delivery of British Academy ECR Network activity at regional level, opening up training opportunities to researchers across the participating institutions. The University also has an [Arts and Humanities Research Council \(AHRC\) Impact Accelerator Account \(IAA\)](#) which enables the University to fund projects and activities to support research impact, including events to bring researchers together with impact leads from other institutions to develop impact training, workshops, conferences and to share resources.

The University of the West of England has also been part of the [BA ECR Network](#) and the [AHRC IAA](#); the IAA has helped to develop good, shared practices across the region. As part of the Southwest and Wales IAA cluster, the institutions involved have co-delivered numerous activities together, including industry events and showcases around 'Immersive Technologies' and 'Building a Green Future through Arts and Humanities Research'. Additionally, the University is involved in two shared Technology Transfer Office (TTO) pilot projects funded by Research England: [SpinOutWest](#), focussed on commercialisation opportunities in the South West of England in the area of health and social care, and [STAGE](#), a national level project supporting creative and social ventures. These pilot projects have provided training and support for commercialisation from university-based research and knowledge activities, both for the researchers themselves as well as the professional services staff supporting them. It has also been an opportunity to share resources and best practices across institutions and build thriving ecosystems that accelerate the translation of research.

8. Conclusions and ideas for future consideration

Conclusions

As this is the first time this survey has been conducted, it aims to establish a baseline to describe researcher development activity across a range of institutions, and to inform discussions about broader questions, such as the appropriate level of professional development activity to be undertaken by professional and academic staff.

Key findings include:

- the study illustrates the importance and challenges of effective evaluation;
- coverage of topics is broadest for personal effectiveness and professional skills and for research students and staff; provision of researcher development opportunities on these topics for professional and technical staff is generally more limited;
- the central researcher development team and doctoral academy lead on operational delivery and most activity is delivered through synchronous sessions; and
- challenges and opportunities for the next five years include training needs relating to AI, as well as its use in training delivery, and collaboration with other institutions.

Additionally, the study indicated that:

- internal motivating factors are similar between Australia and the UK, particularly alignment with institutional strategy and values, the intrinsic value of researcher development activities and aiming to improve research culture. However, understandably external motivations and influential third parties vary by country and include national initiatives relating to research assessment and guidance or standards for researcher development;
- in both Australia and the UK, research committees are responsible for the governance of the researcher development strategy. However, only a minority of institutions have a formal researcher development strategy, and this is often split across a number of different documents;
- institutions vary significantly in the number of institutional units which are described as having primary responsibility for researcher development strategy;
- central researcher development roles are characterised by widespread use of fractional FTE;
- there is no obvious relationship between the size of an institution's researcher community and its level of central researcher development staff resourcing; and
- key barriers to engagement are lack of recognition in workload and lack of awareness.

Areas for future consideration

Based on the findings of this project, both from the survey and from extensive and sustained engagement with the participating institutions throughout the study, eight key areas have been identified for future consideration, potential sector-wide action and for review through a future researcher development survey. These areas for action include:

1. developing **robust and effective approaches to evaluation**, including longitudinal evaluation;
2. exploring change over time in the breadth of **researcher development opportunities offered to professional and technical staff**;

3. exploring options for **optimising the balance of synchronous and asynchronous delivery**, and between online and in-person delivery, and how these vary for different audiences;
4. exploring additional **opportunities for sharing good practice**. In Australia this includes interest in developing a national researcher development framework;
5. considering **how AI will influence researcher development**, both as an emerging area of development need and as a tool for delivery;
6. deepening understanding of **researcher development as a product of, and influence on, research culture** and by extension institutional culture;
7. considering the **highly fractional nature of researcher development activities** within people's roles; and
8. developing further areas for collaboration, including **access to shared training and resources**.

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